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Crowdsourcing biodiversity data from recreational SCUBA divers using Dive Reporter

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ABSTRACT

Monitoring spatiotemporal patterns in marine environments is crucial to ensure a better understanding of ecosystem functioning and, ultimately, for adequate management and marine conservation policies. The lack of resources required for surveys and data acquisition often hampers the availability of long-term datasets, which can be partly mitigated by leveraging citizen science and information technologies to crowdsource data. There is an inherent trade-off between the quality of data obtained using scientific and systematic protocols, and that collected by citizen scientists in an opportunistic fashion. In this pilot study, we explore crowdsourcing data from recreational SCUBA divers using a mobile app to report sightings of a predetermined list of taxa, which have been selected by regional experts as biological indicators. This approach uses post-dive queries that provide some level of standardisation, by focusing on the frequency and abundance of specific taxa, while retaining a recreational dive plan. Additionally, the app also collects metadata on location, number of dives and number of divers enabling normalisation based on “sampling effort”. In this pilot study, the use of the app was tested to compile information on the frequency and abundance of 18 marine taxa selected by local experts based on their conservation status, commercial interest, ecological function and/or their non-indigenous origin. Additionally, a question-based survey was conducted to assess the opinion of users on the app’s usability and the potential value for the diving community/industry, showcasing a high usability score and interest among users. Basic statistical analysis of the data crowdsourced over the 1-month trial illustrates the potential and value of regional monitoring programs using custom lists of taxa and an app to crowdsource data from local dive centres and divers. With the ability to customise the list of taxa used in a region, monitoring programs that leverage mobile apps during post-dive interviews can provide valuable information on species occurrences in any region with active recreational dive operations. Such programs are cost-effective scalable solutions that can easily provide complementary data that can be used to monitor the proliferation of non-indigenous species, to assess the efficacy of conservation measures on protected and endangered species and to assess economically exploited species, as they can track time fluctuations and spatial variations in any conspicuous taxa that scuba divers can report.

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1. Introduction

Earth's biodiversity is undergoing an unprecedented change due to a combination of anthropogenic pressures (Pereira et al., 2012). Our ability to change the current course towards an environmentally sustainable future requires regular assessments of the status and dynamics of biodiversity (Luypaert et al., 2020; Yoccoz et al., 2001). Long-term monitoring of local ecosystems and biodiversity is crucial to detect shifts in key biological traits, in ecological functions and in biodiversity patterns, and to assess whether these are being affected or shaped by climate change and/or human pressures (Giron-Nava et al., 2017). Continuous monitoring enables, for example, the early detection of non-indigenous species' arrival and rapid response to potential biological invasions - an increasing global threat facilitated by human activities and warming seas (Reaser et al., 2020). However, continuously monitoring marine biodiversity presents a challenge due to the distribution, size, and hostile nature of the marine environment (Carstensen, 2014; Hindell et al., 2003). In addition, marine science is generally resource intensive and its funding is usually a major limiting factor (Isensee, 2020; Richardson and Poloczanska, 2008). Combined, these limitations lead the search for alternative, cost-efficient, solutions to complement traditional scientific surveys and to enhance current marine biodiversity monitoring efforts. In complement of scientific surveys, citizen science has been increasingly seen as a cost-effective tool to gather biodiversity data (Theobald et al., 2015; Tulloch et al., 2013) that can be leveraged to inform management decisions (Done et al., 2017; Larson et al., 2020; Marshall et al., 2012; Tiago et al., 2017), while bringing the additional benefit of contributing to ecological literacy of the public (McKinley et al., 2017; Pocock et al., 2018).

Data collection methods can vary considerably among citizen science biodiversity monitoring initiatives and they can be categorised into two groups: (i) systematic monitoring, by engaging and often training a smaller number of citizen scientists who use standardised protocols, and; (ii) opportunistic monitoring, by engaging as many participants as possible, who decide where, when, what and whether to report their observations (Pocock et al., 2018; Brown and Williams, 2019; Henckel et al., 2020). Both approaches have advantages and disadvantages. Opportunistic reporting has the potential to gather larger datasets, but the data quality may be affected due to multiple biases resulting from the lack of standardised monitoring (Brown and Williams, 2019; Van Strien et al., 2013). Options exist to improve the quality of opportunistic data to reduce the effect of bias (Cooper, 2016; Henckel et al., 2020; Kosmala et al., 2016; Wiggins et al., 2011). Systematic monitoring following strict protocols, produces higher-quality data that is suitable for a wide range of uses, including providing background for management decisions (Brown and Williams, 2019; Henckel et al., 2020), however, they generally generate smaller datasets as they engage a smaller audience and require a bigger commitment from participants.

In marine environments, systematic citizen science programs and projects have long been established (Garcia-Soto et al., 2021; Hodgson, 1999; Kelly et al., 2020). These programs can provide high-quality data; however, they often require training and are built around strict protocols that are specifically designed to monitor marine biodiversity and perform coral reef assessments (Done et al., 2017; Theobald et al., 2015). To put it simply, these programs provide training and protocols that are comparable to those used in scientific surveys, training participants to replace skilful researchers and technicians. In the case of volunteering SCUBA divers, strict protocols significantly condition the dive plan and require a level of commitment that often limits the participation rate (Marshall et al., 2012).

Opportunistic citizen science programs and platforms, such as iNaturalist (www.inaturalist.org) or Biodiversity4all (www.biodiversity4all.org), have grown in popularity in recent years and have significantly contributed to scientific knowledge (Happel, 2019; Tiago et al., 2017; Walker and Taylor, 2017). Though not specifically designed as marine citizen science tools, they allow participants to report their

observations in both terrestrial and marine settings, including recreational SCUBA divers. Based on opportunistic sampling, these programs are commonly affected by surveyor bias as participants are more likely to report charismatic and interesting fauna and flora (Roberts et al., 2022). Some initiatives leveraging opportunistic citizen science have attempted to reduce the reporting bias by restricting observations to one target taxonomic group or taxon (Gizzi et al., 2020; Michonneau and Paulay, 2015) or to one location (Happel et al., 2020), however these cases were generally used for very specific research goals. Trying to tackle some of these common issues and limitations of citizen science programs, this study explores a novel approach. It provides elements of standardised monitoring by engaging SCUBA dive operators to interview divers post-dive using a mobile app that limits user reporting to a selected number of taxa (curated by local scientists) within a target geographic location (e.g., Madeira archipelago). This approach ensures systematic reporting on the occurrence and abundance of selected taxa within multiple dive sites, while allowing SCUBA divers to follow a recreational dive plan. The proposed strategy has two main prerequisites: (i) the presence of SCUBA dive operations with organised recreational diving, and (ii) local researchers interested in monitoring local dive sites that can curate the list of target taxa and manage data and outputs. Designed to engage SCUBA dive service providers directly, this strategy has the added advantage of having dive instructors and guides as "in situ validators" which can significantly enhance data quality (Goffredo et al., 2010; Branchini et al., 2015; Mangelli et al., 2021).

Successful citizen science programs often employ high-quality software that is simple to use (Prestopnik and Crowston, 2012; Luna et al., 2018; Skarlatidou et al., 2019; Robinson et al., 2021), and offer benefits to its participants (Cigliano et al., 2015; Kelly et al., 2020; Vann-Sander et al., 2016), for example in the form of data visualisation on a map (Robinson et al., 2021). Building from these previous studies and programs, our approach employs a mobile app with a custom taxa list within a selected area or region. In this pilot study, we explore this concept over a trial period to assess its applicability, value and potential. Additionally, to ensure that the mobile app and the program design follow the best practices mentioned above, we have conducted a usability study with selected dive centres.

In summary, this study tests whether an interview based monitoring program employing a mobile app with a curated list of target taxa can: (i) facilitate and motivate dive operators to actively participate in a interview based long-term citizen science program, and; (ii) ensure the collection of quality data that is useful for local marine researchers and environmental managers.

2. Methods

To test the viability of a monitoring program using elements of standardised data collection tailored for recreational SCUBA divers, we conducted a trial for three months (July–September 2021) at a SCUBA diving centre in Madeira. We used the mobile app Dive Reporter (Radeta et al., 2022) (hereinafter referred to as "the app") as a digital interface for a questionnaire survey with SCUBA divers. The app facilitated data collection from three dive sites but also served to provide standardised elements, including: a pre-established list of taxa curated by experts; a five-level abundance scale with species specific scores, the dive site; and the collection of effort related metadata for each dive (i.e. dive time and number of divers).

For this trial period, the list of target taxa was limited to 18 (Table 1) compiled based on inputs from eight local marine biologists. The researchers were asked to name 10 species they considered most relevant to monitor and to provide information supporting their choices (i.e., asked to specify why each of their choices was important to monitor: because they are non-indigenous and potentially invasive, with special conservation status, with significant economic value or as a known biological/ecological status indicator). All inputs were compiled, and

Table 1

List of marine target taxa included in the trial monitoring program with their scientific name, common name, and taxonomic group.

Scientific Name	Common Name	Group
<i>Asparagopsis</i> sp.	Harpoon weed	Algae
<i>Caulerpa webbiana</i>	Caulerpa seaweed	Algae
<i>Cymodocea nodosa</i>	Seagrass	Algae
<i>Styopodium</i> sp.	Leafy flat-blade algae	Algae
<i>Antipathella</i> sp.	Black coral	Coral
<i>Antipathozoanthus</i> sp.	Bushy encrusting anemone	Coral
<i>Madracis asperula</i>	Green reef coral	Coral
<i>Millepora</i> sp.	Fire Coral	Coral
<i>Octopus vulgaris</i>	Octopus	Mollusc
<i>Umbraculum umbraculum</i>	Warty umbrella snail	Mollusc
<i>Cronius ruber</i>	Swimming crab	Crustacea
<i>Distaplia corolla</i>	Button tunicate	Ascidea
<i>Bodianus scrofa</i>	Red hogfish	Fish
<i>Epinephelus marginatus</i>	Dusky grouper	Fish
<i>Hippocampus</i> sp.	Seahorse	Fish
<i>Sparus aurata</i>	Gilthead seabream	Fish
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	Loggerhead turtle	Reptile
<i>Monachus monachus</i>	Monk seal	Mammal

the taxa were ranked based on the number of times they were listed by the experts. These were then collectively inspected and selected for a final shortlist of 18 taxa (Table S1 in Supplementary Material) that were considered conspicuous (to reduce miss-identification related issues) and that could be used as biological indicators (e.g., part of the IUCN Red List, Marine Strategy Framework Directive indicator, non-indigenous and pest species). Additionally, experts were asked to produce taxa specific abundance scores to be integrated in a five-level abundance scale based on the species biological traits and typical abundances (Table S2 in Supplementary Material). The abundance scores are ranked from 0 (absent) to 4 (highest abundance) for comparability.

This trial was conducted at Manta Diving Center Madeira, located in the south of Madeira Island within the Garajau Partial Nature Reserve, a marine protected area since 1986 with high protection level and with high demand by SCUBA divers. Data collection was conducted by using the app during post-dive interviews with recreational SCUBA divers. The process was interactive, where the interviewer and dive guide used the app to report: (i) the dive site, total number of divers and dive time, and (ii) which of the 18 taxa were sighted and their respective abundance scores. This method of data collection guaranteed that divers' observations were reported correctly, avoiding errors due to app layout, features, or design. All collected data were automatically stored to JSON and synchronised with Wave Labs MySQL database (www.wave-labs.org) using custom API routes based on REST requests.

Additionally, a usability questionnaire survey was conducted in nine local SCUBA diving operators to evaluate the app interface and the interest of local dive operators in using it for monitoring biodiversity in their dive sites. A minimum of two respondents were independently interviewed among dive operators' staff to ensure unbiased individual opinions. The usability survey was developed by adjusting the standard System Usability Scale (SUS) and was conducted with in person interviews during June–July 2022. In addition to the standard SUS questions about app usability, we included questions focusing on the intention of the respondent to use the app after each dive, the expectation of its desirability for clients, the probability of species misidentification and the overall value of the program to the diving community (Table S3 in Supplementary Material). Questions included scaled responses and open-ended queries to get insight into the best way the monitoring program can bring value to the dive community. Responses were compiled and data was used to calculate the average SUS score (Kumar, 2020).

Compiled data was used to assess sightings' frequency for each species (i.e., the percentage of dives where each taxon was reported) and to assess abundance. To consider different "sampling effort" (i.e.,

different number of dives and divers per site) abundance was normalised using reported abundance levels (1–5 scale), dive time and number of divers following:

$$\text{Weighted normalised abundance} = \text{Normalised abundance} / \text{Effort}$$

$$\text{Effort} = \text{Number of divers} \times \text{Dive time}$$

An Analysis of Similarity (ANOSIM) was conducted to test for significant differences in taxa-reported weighted normalised abundances between dive sites based on a Bray-Curtis similarity matrix (Anderson et al., 2008). A shade plot with taxa seriation ($n = 999$) was generated to inspect patterns in weighted normalised abundances by dive site (Clarke et al., 2008; Monteiro et al., 2021). Subsequently, Principal Coordinates Ordination (PCO) analysis with vector overlays was performed to assess: i) ordination patterns of dive site data and ii) correlations between PCO axis with taxa variability in reported data (Clarke et al., 2008). Taxa were ranked based on correlations with PCO and variances of the top six were box-plotted for inspection. All statistical analysis was performed in PRIMER v7 (Clarke et al., 2014; Clarke and Gorley, 2015) with PERMANOVA add-on (Anderson et al., 2008).

3. Results

Usability. A total of 20 respondents (e.g., owners, instructors, and other staff) from nine dive centres (located on Madeira and Porto Santo Islands) completed the usability survey. The average SUS score from all 20 responses is 78, considered a good SUS result (Kumar, 2020) (Table S4 in Supplementary Material).

Overall results (Fig. 1) show that respondents largely agree with positive statements about the monitoring program and the app (odd-numbered questions) and largely disagree with negative ones (even-numbered questions). The most positive feedback was received on questions regarding app simplicity, recognition of the monitored species and the program bringing value to the diving community. The least positive feedback was regarding the timing and effort spent on post-dive interviews and data collection (Fig. 1). Additionally, we compiled and ranked common responses to the final open question regarding how the monitoring program could best contribute to the dive centre (Table S5 in Supplementary Material). Most commonly mentioned suggestions were: to include additional and/or more emblematic species on the taxa list (40%); to complement the monitoring program and app with a website that would include a map and sighting data (40%); to create a poster and other dissemination material (40%), and; to advertise the program and participating dive centres on social media (20%). The taxa that were most frequently requested included: Batoidea (e.g., butterfly ray, common eagle ray), *Aulostomus strigosus* (Atlantic trumpetfish), *Seriola Dumerili* (Greater amberjack), *Sphyrna sphyraena* (European barracuda), *Sparisoma cretense* (Mediterranean parrotfish), *Thalassoma pavo* (Ornate wrasse) and species belonging to the Muraenidae family (Moray eels).

Biodiversity. During the trial monitoring, a total of 42 surveys from 6 dive sites were collected. Dive sites where only one survey was submitted were excluded from further analysis, resulting in 39 valid surveys from three dive sites. The three dive sites were Arena, Lavafinger and Galo, all directly accessible from the dive centre and located next to each other from the west (Arena) to east (Galo) within the Garajau Partial Nature Reserve (Fig. 2).

Report analysis reveals a higher frequency of *Asparagopsis* sp., *S. zonale* and *O. vulgaris* in Lavafinger and Galo compared to Arena. On the other hand, *S. aurata* and *E. marginatus* are reported more frequently in Arena than in the two other dive sites. *B. scrofa* is less frequent in Lavafinger than in the two other dive sites, and Galo has a higher frequency of reports with *U. umbraculum*.

An inspection of a shadeplot with normalised weighted abundances (Fig. 3) revealed that no major pattern or gradient can be identified between sites. However, some differences are visible, namely Lavafinger

Fig. 1. Chart representing the results of the modified SUS for the app.

Fig. 2. Map of the monitored area with the approximate delineation of the dive sites. The charts below each dive site represent the total frequencies (%) of each taxon reported for each dive site.

exhibits lower values for *S. aurata* and *B. scrofa* and higher values of *Asparagopsis* sp. and *O. vulgaris*, compared to Arena. This absence of easily identified patterns and the presence of small differences in the shadeplot is corroborated by ANOSIM results, where no overall significant differences were detected (Table S6 in Supplementary Material) and where pairwise tests showcase a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) only between Lavafinger and Arena reported values.

Trying to better understand the ordination, a PCO plot was generated (Fig. 4) illustrating: i) a clustered distribution of samples indicating a lower variance and more homogeneity between samples in Galo, followed by Lavafinger and then Arena (with samples more spread out along PCO1 and PCO2); ii) there is greater overlap between Galo and Lavafinger samples (especially on PCO1 axis) and less overlap between Arena and Lavafinger, both supporting the pairwise significant differences found under ANOSIM and; iii) how the six taxa that correlate

higher with sample ordination vary along PCO1 and PCO2 axes (collectively explaining 51.1% of the total variation). Correlation vector overlays suggest that differences found in sample ordination (Fig. 4) are mostly due to higher values of the fishes *S. aurata*, *E. marginatus* and *B. scrofa* in Arena and lower values of *S. zonale* (i.e., frequency weighted normalised abundance). The algae *Asparagopsis* sp. and the common octopus (*O. vulgaris*) were highly correlated with the PCO2 axis (explaining 20.4% of total variation) but showed little variation along PCO1 (explaining 30.7% of total variation).

Six taxa were selected for box plot (Fig. 5) analysis of normalised weighted abundance because of their significance in PCO analysis. Variance in reported weighted normalised abundance exhibits the same tendencies as in the shadeplot and PCO plot above.

An inspection of boxplots for the reported weighted normalised abundance of these six taxa (Fig. 5) illustrate how these taxa vary across

Fig. 3. Shadeplot with normalised weighted abundances reported for each of selected taxa (with $n > 0$).

Fig. 4. Principal Coordinate Ordination (PCO) plot of normalised weighted abundance and correlation between the 6 selected taxa (vectors) and PCO axes (black lines).

Fig. 5. Weighted abundance of 6 selected taxa. Box plot with first quartile, median and third quartile, minimum and maximum as whiskers and points as outliers.

the three sites. Reports from Arena show a lower abundance of *Asparagopsis sp.* and slightly higher values for both *S. aurata* and *E. marginatus* than those reported from other dive sites (Fig. 5). Reports from Lavafinger suggest significantly lower occurrence of *S. aurata* and *B. scrofa* in this site, whereas Galo has higher reported values for the two algae most contributing to sample ordination (i.e., *S. zonale* and *Asparagopsis sp.*).

Both Lavafinger and Galo are reported to be significantly more abundant in *Asparagopsis sp.* than the Arena site. *O. vulgaris* is reported as slightly more abundant in Lavafinger, while Galo shows the highest abundance of *S. zonale*.

4. Discussion

Citizen science is increasingly becoming an important tool that enables cost-effective biodiversity monitoring and initiatives oriented at marine environments (Garcia-Soto et al., 2021; Kelly et al., 2020). In SCUBA oriented citizen science initiatives, a trade-off persists between two approaches to data collection: opportunistic reporting allows simplicity and participation of recreational SCUBA divers, but is prone to noisy data, while systematic surveys with standard protocols offer higher data quality, but often create barriers to participation. In this study, we tested a novel approach that provides elements of standardised data collection, while retaining a recreational SCUBA dive plan, by leveraging a mobile app with a custom species list to conduct post-dive interviews and compile data.

A key factor for the success of citizen science initiatives is to maintain volunteers' motivation and ensure long-term participation and engagement (Newman et al., 2011). Based on the usability survey, all responders found the app easy to use and not complex, which is encouraging for the implementation of a long-term program. Moreover, most respondents were confident that users, with assistance from dive guides and dive staff could correctly identify all target taxa, reducing

risks of miss-identification related issues and ensuring data consistency. In addition, respondents overwhelmingly agreed that a monitoring program based on the use of a mobile app would bring added value to the local diving community and that it would be appreciated by their clients, which is an additional promising factor for the feasibility of a long-term monitoring program with the support of local dive centres.

Despite the positive feedback, some concerns were also raised with the level of commitment and the added task loading of using the app to collect data after every dive. This hesitation is likely related to operational schedules and constraints (i.e., time availability), facilities characteristics (i.e., space to comfortably conduct the post-dive survey) and divers' willingness to participate. Nevertheless, we consider that even if dive centres participation is restricted to some dives (e.g., 20–30% of the dive trips and guided dives), the data collected will still be of great value as the program will aim to promote a long-term engagement of multiple dive operators, ensuring long-term and consistent crowdsourced datasets. In summary, a SUS score of 78 is a good indicator, but monitoring program coordinators (e.g., researchers) must ensure regular stakeholder interactions and engagement to secure and motivate their continued participation.

App usability, stakeholder interest and participation are crucial to secure program implementation feasibility, however, they do not guarantee that crowdsourced data can be used for science or management purposes. Following the strategy and approach outlined for this study, data collected during post-dive "interviews" can be used for research and/or management if: (i) the list of species selected is restricted to conspicuous taxa, and (ii) reported data can be used to assess spatial and/or temporal patterns. During this trial, which was tailored for Madeira island and a local dive centre, a custom list of 18 taxa selected by experts assures that fluctuations and differences in their reports can be used as key indicators, such as frequency and abundance of: NIS (e.g. the potentially invasive *Cronius ruber* crab), commercial

species (e.g. *Octopus vulgaris*) or species with special conservation status (e.g. the red-listed dusky grouper, *Epinephelus marginatus*). Similarly, other new and custom monitoring programs can be developed and tailored for the needs and specificities of other geographical areas, or different research teams. This flexibility in designing tailored programs with custom lists of species makes this approach reusable for dive centres and operators to easily assist in monitoring local marine biodiversity in other locations, while preserving common elements for standardised data collection.

Data of sufficient quality and temporal scale acquired with the help of citizen scientists finds wide application in ecology and conservation management. It has been used in analysing seasonal patterns in ocean and coastal ecosystems (Thomas et al., 2014), evaluating the efficacy of conservation measures (Wijewardhana et al., 2022) and monitoring marine biological invasions (Giovos et al., 2019).

In our case, long-term monitoring programs using the approach described have several potential use cases relevant to marine science and conservation management: (i) monitoring of marine biological invasions, including early detection and rapid response and evaluation of invasive species management policies, (ii) vulnerable and protected species monitoring and conservation policies evaluation, (iii) economically exploited species monitoring, and (iv) evaluation of ecosystem services provided or costs caused by an individual species or a group of species.

The purpose of this initial trial monitoring program was not to gather sufficient data to analyse Madeira's marine biodiversity. Instead, we aimed to demonstrate that the data obtained from the app has the potential for time-series and spatial analyses that can provide additional understanding of the local conditions. This trial study allowed us to spot differing patterns in taxa occurrences; however, the limited time and spatial scales of the study does not allow us to draw ecological and/or biological explanations to the differences and patterns detected. Nevertheless, despite the limited dataset, it is possible to showcase and demonstrate possible analysis and applications of a future long-term program.

Our results point out a significant difference between Arena and Lavafinger dive sites caused mainly by the following taxa: *Asparagopsis* sp., *O. vulgaris*, *S. aurata*, *S. zonale*, *B. scrofa* and *E. marginatus*. This is possibly due to differences in benthic topology in the observed areas. Both Arena and Galo are open areas with the seafloor covered in boulders, with Galo's easternmost part delineated by a vertical cliff with underwater caves. Lavafinger consists of an underwater feature made of volcanic rock that was created by lava flows and spreads horizontally, roughly perpendicular to the shore. Long-term data collection on more dive sites can provide additional clues on the mechanisms and factors shaping these differences by using multivariate correlative analysis (Clarke et al., 2014; Monteiro et al., 2021).

Significant differences are partly shaped by a higher abundance/frequency of some motile species. In this case, *S. aurata* is showing up more in Arena, while *B. scrofa* and *E. marginatus* are reported to be more abundant in both Arena and Galo. Sessile species of marine algae, *Asparagopsis* sp. and *S. zonale*, are reported to be more abundant in Lavafinger and Galo, which may be related to their preference for rocky benthic substrate (Altamirano et al., 2008; Casas et al., 2021; Kitayama, 2022). *Octopus vulgaris*, while highly motile, tends to prefer some structure, such as the crevices (Guerra et al., 2014) of Lavafinger and Galo, to the fully open topology of Arena. In summary, the data shows that Lavafinger appears to be more dominated by *Asparagopsis* sp. and *S. zonale* with higher abundance of *O. vulgaris*, while the occurrence of indicator/target fish species is considerably lower. In contrast, data reported from Arena suggests a much higher abundance/frequency of target fish species and a significantly lower coverage by macroalgae. Reports from Galo, which has both an open area and a rocky-reef feature, illustrate a habitat where macroalgae are commonly abundant while also reporting a moderate abundance of target fish species. The differences between dive sites and the patterns detected are somehow

consistent with the substrate topology of these three dive sites, corroborating the roles of substrate, topography, and depth in shaping local communities (Monteiro et al., 2021). Additionally, data inspection and basic analysis showcases the potential benefit of a long-term monitoring by local dive operators using the app, where time series and spatial patterns in the abundance/frequency of key indicator taxa can easily be compiled.

A good example of the applications of our approach during a long-term monitoring program in Madeira would be the ability to assess distribution, spread and abundance/frequency of non-indigenous sea bream *S. aurata* (introduced in Madeira for aquaculture; Alves and Alves, 2002; Parretti et al., 2023). Leveraging a mobile app and post-dive interviews, researchers and managers could obtain temporal and spatial data on *S. aurata* sightings' frequency and reported abundance over time and compare them with native species that might be influenced by the enhanced trophic competition at one of their life stages (Parretti et al., 2023). Moreover, the app can also be applied to assess the effects of the arrival of a NIS with highly disruptive potential on local marine environments, such as the recent *Rugulopteryx okamurae* arrival in the region (Bernal-Ibáñez et al., 2022).

Another example would be to track the abundance and frequency in reports of *B. scrofa* and assess the efficacy of the measures recently implemented for the protection of the species (Conselho do Governo Regional, 2022). This is also the case for other protected and charismatic species, such as the dusky grouper *E. marginatus*, the loggerhead turtle *C. caretta*, the monk seal *M. monachus* and the seahorse *Hippocampus* sp. Additionally, the app can also be leveraged to keep track of dive activities, number of divers and dive times enabling an evaluation of SCUBA-related ecosystem services.

To better accommodate the needs of dive operators, while maintaining usability for research and management, the trial included a query for dive staff to detail how to enhance a future long-term monitoring program. Most of the received suggestions were already planned to be included in a full-scale monitoring program, although these were not yet part of the trial. Frequency maps, such as the one showcased in Fig. 1, would allow the dive centre to identify dive sites with the highest probability of encountering specific taxa or keep statistics about the number of times these taxa have been observed throughout a year. This information would benefit the dive centres for marketing purposes, as recreational SCUBA divers usually prefer areas where they can see charismatic species (Grafeld et al., 2016). The query also confirmed that a poster presence for each dive centre with the target taxa that are part of the monitoring project could help as a reminder and a motivation tool to increase the interest of SCUBA diving clients and incentivize dive guides to conduct post-dive debriefings with the app. The same applies to social media mentions, which could also promote the development of communities among researchers, conservationists, professional SCUBA divers and citizen scientists.

One of the most important suggestions, from most interviewees, was the request to include more charismatic species in the list of taxa. This is based on the commercial nature of the dive centres and the general preference and demand for such species. However, these may not be the best indicator species and local scientists may prefer to target taxa based on ecological function or role. Ultimately, considering the importance in maintaining dive operators engaged and participating, it is crucial that researchers and dive operators are active participants in the program design and strategy, including in establishing which taxa to target and report. Ideally one can include species that are both charismatic and of scientific interest and, if necessary, compromise with a few species that meet only one of these criteria. This commitment to find a solution was also considered during interviews, resulting in a new list of 24 taxa, with six additional species suggested by the respondents.

Despite the numerous advantages and potential of the outlined strategy and the use of a mobile app in custom designed monitoring programs, it is important to consider the caveats and limitations of such an approach. Data gathering during this trial study was facilitated by an

interviewer who was able to interact with dive staff and divers in person and detect some behaviours that may impact data quality. One of these behaviours is the tendency to underreport marine species seen as common and overreport rare and charismatic species. An example could be the hesitation of citizen scientists to report a dive where the only taxa observed were the algae *Asparagopsis* sp. and *S. zonale*, while they were eager to report the sighting of *C. caretta* or *E. marginatus*. This behaviour brings obvious bias to the acquired data and has been repeatedly observed in other research using data from citizen scientists or students (Bonney et al., 2009; Galloway et al., 2006; Gardiner et al., 2012). In our case study and future program, reporting bias would be mitigated in two ways: i) by including a checklist of conspicuous species, and; ii) by ensuring the dive guide or staff take on the role of interviewer and curator while using the app as a tool for post-dive debriefing. Combined, these two steps ensure that there is a specific checklist to cross out and that the interview is embedded in regular operations of the dive centre.

Another aspect that could influence data quality is the possibility of misidentifying species that are less known to the citizen scientists (Austen et al., 2016; Freiwald et al., 2018). This is especially true because the app does not require submission of photographic evidence, which could be validated by experts (Kosmala et al., 2016) or using machine learning (Saoud et al., 2020). Once again, by relying on the dive guide to conduct the interview, there is some level of validation of the species sighted and reported, as they are often knowledgeable and experienced in local fauna and flora. This approach has also been used in previous studies as a safeguard for data quality (Branchini et al., 2015; Mangelli et al., 2021) and it is corroborated by our usability survey findings.

Finally, the success of any future monitoring program depends on the willingness and motivation of the dive centres and staff to regularly participate and commit over long period of time. While the survey from this case study produced favourable results, only by launching a full-scale monitoring program will we be able to assess the actual participation rate. We believe dive guides and dive operators will continue to be motivated if the program genuinely provides useful tools that facilitate and/or enhance their performance and their jobs, while keeping their clients interested. This will require that new knowledge and enhanced understanding of local marine environments gained through their collaboration and participation must be channelled back to the dive centres in an easy-to-understand way that they can leverage during their business or operations (e.g., as species frequency maps and time charts). Tools aimed at generating publicity for the monitoring program and helping to build a local community between marine researchers and recreational SCUBA divers, such as posters, distributable tablets, and social media, should also be a priority to ensure the longevity of the program. Another crucial step will be determining the best way to scale up beyond Madeira region, which will entail an active collaboration with researchers in other geographic regions, where they can engage local dive operators and customise a list of indicator species to monitor. Ultimately, this approach can be used and leveraged beyond borders and contribute, not only to a better local and regional understanding of marine habitats, but also provide clues for macro spatial scaled understanding of biodiversity patterns and trends.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Matej Buzinkai: Conceptualisation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Formal analysis, Visualisation, Supervision. **Marko Radeta:** Conceptualisation, Methodology, Software, Data curation, Resources, Supervision. **Claudio Rodrigues:** Software, Data curation. **Francisco Silva:** Software, Data curation. **Ruben Freitas:** Software, Data curation. **Sahar Chebaane:** Methodology, Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Paola Parretti:** Methodology, Investigation, Visualisation, Data curation, Writing – review & editing. **Susanne Schäfer:** Methodology, Conceptualisation, Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Rodrigo Silva:** Methodology, Investigation. **Francesca Gizzi:** Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **Silvia Almeida:** Formal analysis, Resources. **Sonia K.M. Gueroun:** Methodology, Investigation, Visualisation, Writing – review & editing. **João Canning-Clode:** Conceptualisation, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **João Gama Monteiro:** Conceptualisation, Methodology, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Formal analysis, Visualisation, Supervision, Project administration.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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